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SIMULATIONS: HANDS-ON EDUCATION AS A SPATIAL LEARNING TOOL.

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ABSTRACT

The Sight, Sound + Movement accessibility workshop offers architecture students the opportunity to simulate various disabilities. Simulations include reduced/loss of vision and mobility impairments such as a single user wheelchair, companion wheelchair and temporary impairments including a leg brace with crutches. The exercises conducted during this multi-day workshop are not intended to convey the actual experience of the impairment or “what it’s like to be blind” but rather how the built environment and routine design decisions impact the user’s ability to use, experience and navigate space.

Interactions with toilet stalls, sinks and accessories, entry doors, stairs, elevators, ramps, parking and building materials are just a few of the opportunities students are exposed to during the simulations.

Keywords: Way-finding, Accessibility, Simulation.

Figure 1. Single wheelchair user and a companion wheelchair user experiencing the roughness of various sidewalk materials.

GENERAL PREMISE AND CONCEPTS

The goal of the Sight, Sound + Movement (SS+M) accessibility workshop is to raise awareness of the personal impact design decisions have on people with disabilities in the everyday world. The workshop strives to communicate how environments can sometimes be difficult, uncomfortable and unsafe. Another goal of this work is to impact the local community. This is achieved by a) knowing the awareness gained by design students will add to their personal and professional development; b) knowing this new awareness will influence actions that may impact the designed environment; and c) knowing the local community can become a more universally aware environment. Each of these learning opportunities makes the future designers keen of the user’s needs for certain products and services.

Figure 2. Identifying difficult transitions from indoors to outdoors. Uneven thresholds and cross-slopes make for dangerous situations for both wheelchair users and those with visual impairments.

Figure 3. Poor design and planning makes for a tight path of travel from the accessible parking to the entry ramp.

SIMULATIONS AS A TEACHING TOOL

Although simulation exercises have been found to stimulate interest in a topic they have also been reputed to change opinions, increase empathy, increase self-awareness, and increase tolerance for ambiguity (Brendemeier & Greenblat, 1981). However, a specific simulation experience is not the same for every participant. What any single learner might experience depends on a great number of factors. These factors may include the similarity between the simulation experience and the participant's anticipation of the experience, the participant's learning styles, and their previous experiences. Other factors affecting performance may be the teaching style of the instructor, the structure and methods behind the exercises and the intended outcomes.

During simulations, participants "carry out functions associated with their roles and with the settings in which they find themselves. The outcomes of the simulation are not determined by chance or luck. Instead, participants experience consequences that follow from the actions" within the simulation (Hertel & Millis, 2002). Simulations as a teaching tool have been criticized as inappropriate in the context of emerging paradigms of disability studies. A simulation creates a representation of elements of reality to develop a learning activity so participants develop skills, gain knowledge or change their attitude about that reality (Duke, 1986; Hertel & Millis, 2002). Critics of simulations often point to the lack of valid tools to measure specific outcomes (Remus, 1991). Another common criticism is that

even carefully designed tools that measure intended learning may neglect to measure unintended learning, sometimes referred to as the hidden curriculum, that can be potentially quite negative (Gay, 2000).

The use of simulations has been tested and accepted widely throughout the factions of social sciences and behavioral sciences. However, when considering architecture as a static art form, the rate of change is much slower and usually reactionary. Ideally, the experiences of participants are as realistic as possible. Whether conducted by face-to-face meetings or via computers, simulations can provide an engaging learning strategy within academic, organizational and business settings (Hunter & Clark, 1977; Randel, Morris, Wetzel, & Whitehill, 1992). One contentious issue that seems to recur is that of simulating the physical environment through computer generated images, and the lack of hands-on experience often necessary to truly evaluate real-world or issues in the built environment.

Social workers, medical doctors, special education teachers, disabled student service administrators, vocational rehabilitation counselors, and other professionals have historically focused on an individual's functional limitations. Understanding the long history of investigating user abilities by these fields of study helped develop the Sight, Sound + Movement workshop. The instructor specifically suggests to the participants to not take the simulated disabilities personally but rather to use such opportunities as a future design tool when creating spaces for all users.

Figure 4. Students are required to participate in at least 3 different exercises (2 indoors and 1 outdoors).

Figure 5. Although the students are not asked to transfer from the wheelchair to the water closet it is evident that the spaces often provided in the toilet rooms are too confined.

Simulations, as often used in disability awareness training, involve "imitating" a physical, sensory, or cognitive impairment for a limited amount of time, and are sometimes followed by a discussion to explore what was learned (French, 1992; Scullion, 1999). However, outcomes are not always positive and may be detrimental. In actuality, most disability-related simulations are designed to result in negative feelings. By disabling participants and simulating problematic experiences, given their new limitations (Clore & Jeffery, 1972; French, 1992), participants learn how difficult it is to maneuver a

wheelchair or see where they are walking. These simulations often focus on what people with disabilities cannot do rather than on what they can do with appropriate access, technology, or skills (Clore & Jeffery, 1972). This approach is very similar to the exercises composed in the SS+M workshop.

In the setting of an architecture school, the students are required to simulate three different disabilities; impaired vision through the use of impairment goggles, mobility impairment through the use of a wheelchair, and temporary impairment by way of a leg brace and crutches. However, the intended outcomes stated from the very beginning of the workshop is not to experience the disability or impairments but rather to experience the built environment around them as they move about the spaces.

In developing the SS+M Workshop it was recognized that when these simulation exercises are implemented people would tend to focus more on the physical disability and not the surrounding environment. As stated in an article by John W. Smith (1997), the fear of wrongly portraying the many disabilities or impairments is real. The SS+M

Figure 6. Architects often overlook the fact that people do not always travel alone. Be it those who need assistance or a group of friends the width of many pathways are uncomfortable or obstructed.

Workshop factors this into the sessions by introducing the participants to a variety of people with disabilities who can better explain their experiences. Stories include a high-school student who has been a wheelchair user his entire life, and an older adult who has recently lost his vision at the age of 72. The opportunity to hear from people who explain that there is no pity or sorrow needed, nor expected, helps to alleviate the awkwardness many may feel when participating in disability simulations. Helping to set the tone of the conversation is hearing someone with a disability say “it isn’t the impairment that is the problem, but, the struggles of living in an inaccessible world”. This attitude is what keeps the students focused on the learned outcomes of the simulations.

In addition to the disability exercises the workshop requires other research by each student such as photo journaling “good” and “bad” examples of accessible architecture, reading the Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990 and presenting products and services that best demonstrate universal design. By carefully planning group discussions and conducting an exit interview at the end of the workshop, the students are better prepared to continue in the architecture design studio.

ACCEPTING SIMULATIONS

“The reality is this: nondisabled persons can never understand what it is like to have a disability. Jumping in a wheelchair for a few minutes, wearing a blindfold, and stuffing cotton in one’s ears does not make a person understand life with a disability” (Brew-Parrish, 1997). Brew-Parrish makes a good point that there is no substitute for the real thing. The same arguments can be made for a wheelchair user, an obese person, and someone of a taller stature. Fortunately, the SS+M Workshops stress this point and attempt to satisfy the critics by removing the personal connection between the user and the disability. Instead the simulations highlight the user and the spatial environment. Until designers begin to design for the wide range of people instead of the average healthy male then the need for simulations may always be around.

Figure 7. Lack of transfer space, grab bars and toilet accessories.

Figure 8. Inadequate headroom height, missing grab bars and toilet accessories.

Figure 9: Architects often overlook furniture locations and movable items which can become hazards and obstacles within the path of travel.

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